

Agility within the scope of bio refineries: Identifying main characteristics and key factors for agile bio refineries

Juan Henriques¹, Rui Dias¹, Doroteya Vladimirova² and Marco Estrela³

¹ *Low Carbon & Resource Efficiency, R&Di, Instituto de Soldadura e Qualidade, Rua do 8 Mirante, 33, 4415-491 Grijó, Portugal*

² *Institute for Manufacturing, Department of Engineering, University of Cambridge, 17 Charles Babbage Road, Cambridge CB3 0FS, UK*

³ *Low Carbon & Resource Efficiency, R&Di, Instituto de Soldadura e Qualidade, Av. Prof. Dr. Cavaco Silva, 258, Taguspark, 2740-120 Oeiras, Portugal*

Abstract

In the last 20 years, the development of biorefineries has been increasing around the world. This increase is mainly due to the potential benefits presented by this type of plant, namely, the reduction of raw materials, reduction of operational costs, and its adaptability that allows valorization of diverse feedstocks. Nevertheless, the implementation of biorefineries still faces some significant challenges such as appropriate availability of raw materials (quality and quantity), feasibility in the product supply chain, economies of scale, and the difficult territorial anchoring. Some of those problems are related to the current approach taken to implement biorefineries that frequently lay in the perspective of developing a large-scale plant under a single large-scale investment. An interesting approach to solve some of those problems is the introduction of the agility concept in biorefineries, i.e. the promotion of agile biorefineries (AB). Agile biorefineries are flexible plants, where a reconfiguration of the process is achieved by switching equipment inside a single standalone plant, therefore they achieve this agility by adapting configurations, varying feedstocks, and even changing operating conditions throughout time. Despite relevant efforts that have been made to promote a definition of agile biorefineries, the authors consider that it is still necessary to contribute to a common definition of this concept by identifying its main characteristics, which have not been clearly established. This study has two main objectives, firstly to contribute to the common definition of the AB concept and the identification of its core characteristics. Secondly, to identify the key factors in the process of implementing an Agile Biorefinery. To achieve these objectives, this study is based on a mixed approach that joins a systematic literature review with expert consultation. The main results of this study are: (i) contribution for the common definition; (ii) identification and description of the fundamental characteristics of an agile biorefinery; and (iii) a framework of key factors (enablers and challenges) in the implementation

process of AB. The results presented in this paper could be a valuable tool for stakeholders that intend to implement agile biorefineries, especially for those who have no previous experience in this area.

Keywords: Agile bio refineries, agility, circular economy, key factors.

1. Introduction

In recent years the implementation of biorefineries has increased in the world. One of the most accepted definitions of biorefining was given by the International Energy Agency defining biorefining as “the sustainable processing of biomass into a spectrum of marketable products and energy” (Bauer, Coenen, Hansen, McCormick, & Palgan, 2017). The IEA Bioenergy also defines bio refineries as “the sustainable processing of biomass into a spectrum of marketable bio-based products (food/feed ingredients, chemicals, materials) and bioenergy (biofuels, power and/or heat) Factory (Ree & Jong, 2019).

The implementation of biorefineries presents several benefits in various areas such as environmental, social, and economic. Among these benefits are reduction of raw materials, reduction of operational costs, and its adaptability that allows valorization of diverse feedstocks, among others. Nevertheless, the implementation of biorefineries still faces some significant challenges such as appropriate raw material availability (quality and quantity), feasibility in the product supply chain, economies of scale, and difficult territorial anchoring. Despite the increase in biomass processing projects and initiatives over these last two decades, the development of biorefineries is significantly slowed down because of several constraints (Houngbé, Barthe-Delanoë, & Négny, 2019).

A promising approach to overcoming these challenges and promoting biorefineries is the implementation of agile biorefineries (Houngbé et al., 2019). Agile biorefineries have been defined as flexible plants, where a reconfiguration of the process is achieved by switching equipment inside a single standalone plant, therefore they achieve agility by adapting configurations, varying feedstocks, and even changing operating conditions throughout time.

The current approach to biorefining is through a large-scale plant under a single large-scale investment. However, this appears to be a difficult approach to replicate. The new cases and associated process technologies of de-constructing and re-constructing biological feedstocks allows us to design and build new, lower cost, agile bio-refineries that can take in a variety of inputs and create a variety of outputs. Rather than a single, large-scale plant dedicated to a specific waste stream, we now imagine a set of independent manufacturing plants that can collaborate and compete to maximise the total value (economic, environmental & social) of a waste stream. Furthermore, there are no existing examples of agile bio-refineries globally and our research seeks to make the first step towards identifying key parameters and requirements for the creation of an agile bio-refinery, as well as outline the key barriers that need to be overcome by industry and wider society.

This study has two main objectives, firstly to contribute to a common definition of the AB concept and the identification of its core characteristics. Secondly, the paper aims to identify key factors involved in the process of implementing an Agile Biorefinery. In order to accomplish these objectives, the paper poses the following research questions:

RQ1: What is a common definition of an Agile Biorefinery and what are the fundamental characteristics of an agile biorefinery?

RQ2: What are the key factors (enablers and barriers) in the implementation of AB?

This paper is structured into four sections, a first and an introductory section for the approach and objectives of the research. A section to present the methodology followed in this study. A result section to present the common definition of AB, main characteristics, and implementation key factors. In the last section, conclusions are drawn.

2. Methodology

Research strategy

The first step in this study was to define methodology research that would allow the achievement of the proposed objectives. Figure 1 represents the proposed methodology.

Figure 1 Levels of the literature review

This study adopts a research strategy that combines a literature review and expert consultation to identify a common definition for AB and the key factor in its implementation process.

Literature review and expert consultation

The objective of the literature review is to reveal the common trends between AB and other concepts (such as biorefineries, modular biorefineries and integrated biorefineries) (i); the possible enablers and barriers within the scope of AB (ii); and the contribution of other concepts to AB (iii). A search was conducted in the search engines Scopus and Web of Science on three different levels. Figure 2 shows the different levels of the literature review with the subject addressed and the number references identified.

Figure 1 Levels of the literature review

Our main information source for the case studies characterization was based on scientific peer-reviewed journal articles. A complementary search was also developed through Internet searches for technical reports and technical documentation of European initiatives, such as European projects and reports. In addition, an expert consultation was performed.

In parallel to the literature review, an expert consultation was designed and performed. In this process have been interviewed 3 experts related to the field of implementation of bio refineries. The three experts selected have a similar profile, with a strong technical background in the practical implementation of biorefineries. This consultation was performed through an interview of approximately one hour. In this interview we address 4 main topics: the concept proposal for AB (i), the main characteristic of AB (ii); key factors for the AB implementation process (enablers and barriers) and the main opportunities of this concept. This consultation enabled the identification of critical aspects that were not registered in the scientific literature and provided important insight for our research.

Identification of key factors

Once the common trend and concept of agile biorefineries were identified, the next step in the research was to identify the potential key factors involved in the implementation process of agile bio refineries. For this purpose, the identification of enablers and barriers (Key factors) was developed through a methodology of 3 sequential steps to identify which were the enablers and barriers associated with the AB concept:

- i. Identify key factors in the agile bio refineries. Establish a state of the art in key factors regarding similar concepts (For instance Bio refineries and modular bio refineries)
- ii. Use expert consultation as a gathering information method
- iii. Use comparative analysis in order to identify the key factors for AB

3. Study Results

A common definition for Agile Bio refineries (AB)

Taking into account the previous background in the definition of agile bio refineries and the inputs of our research, the authors consider that an AB is a flexible plant, where a reconfiguration of the process is achieved by switching equipment inside a single standalone plant, therefore they achieve this agility by adapting configurations, varying feedstocks, and even changing operating conditions throughout time.

In this sense agile restorative biorefinery involves a relatively low capital investment modular (adaptable) facility, deployed locally (uses local, short-distance available resources), capable of utilising different feedstocks (flexible), including wastes, in a small-scale but high yield production, which works in tandem and focusing in generating value across all stakeholders. In the following section, the core characteristics will be addressed.

Figure 3 Restorative agile biorefinery concept characteristics

Flexible and Reconfigurable

From a manufacturing standpoint, flexibility attains the capacity of how fast the company converts its process(es) from making an old line of products to producing a new product. Early definitions are based on the notion of adaptability to uncertainties (ElMaraghy, 2005), which still retains much of the essence given to flexible manufacturing systems. The ability to change a production schedule, modify a part, or handle multiple parts. The ability to rapidly increase or decrease production levels of shift capacity from one product to another. The reconfigurable manufacturing paradigm was introduced as a necessity to cope with relatively large fluctuations in product demand and mix caused by market disturbances (Koren et al., 1999).

To successfully construct the concept of agile biorefinery, one must take these factors into account and consider their integration into the design, planning and operational management of biorefineries. Biorefineries need to be designed for flexibility so that they can adapt easily to changes in feedstock supply and/or demand for value-added products (Villemont et al., 2017).

Feedstocks and technology selection for agile

A biorefinery is typically defined by the type of feedstock and conversion process applied (Ubando, Felix, & Chen, 2020). The first-generation feedstocks are already very compromised due to global food supply shortages and have been reported to increase the prices of food and animal feed (Sims, Mabee, Saddler, & Taylor, 2010). This tendency is being aggravated by the climate crisis and increased human population, thus not allowing concomitant use for sustainable biorefining.

In this sense, the authors consider that efforts should be directed towards non-food competing feedstocks, which means using biowastes and by-products from several agro-food and non-agro-food sectors in cross-sectorial exchanges. Among those, stream materials such as lignocellulosic materials, green fertilizers, and other farm residues, kitchen waste, agro-food waste, industrial waste, and forestry wastes can be highlighted (Naik, Goud, Rout, & Dalai, 2010). A waste biorefinery is said of capable producing fuels, power, heat, and value-added products (Nizami et al., 2017). For example, the use of lignocellulosic materials allows different platforms to be deployed for the extraction of intermediate products such as lignin, and hemicellulose, which could be further processed for value-added products such as bacterial cellulose, biopolymers, and bio solvents (Takkellapati, Li, & Gonzalez, 2018). Consequently, these have several uses by different industrial sectors such as the medical, pharmaceutical, textile, chemical, among others.

To take advantage of the relatively low processing capacity (due to scale), the production system needs to be highly efficient in terms of value-added. The production processes and thus, technology selection needs to be carefully selected, to allow the production of high-margin products at minimal resource use. There are reports of reduced capital costs in these integrative multi-productive systems (Olguin-Maciél, Singh, Chable-Villacis, Tapia-Tussell, & Ruiz, 2020), and of effectiveness in maximising biomass yield and efficiency (Pinales-Márquez et al., 2021). Not all technologies are appropriate for agile biorefining, and consequently, a key design requirement is to effectively optimize chosen supply (raw material) and the portfolio of products to be produced. The biochemical pathway seems promising from a small-scale and low-cost standpoint (Igbokwe, Ezugworie, Onwosi, Aliyu, & Obi, 2022). Several studies also consider the use of biomass fractionation technologies to optimize efficiency (Sun et al., 2018; Xu et al., 2020).

Small-scale, modularity and decentralisation

Larger centralized processing plants benefit from economies of scale due to reduced marginal costs, better processing yields, and returns on investment. For these reasons, small-scale processes greatly

defy economies of scale. However, (Bruins & Sanders, 2012) argue that economies of scale may not be as important in the biomass-based sector as it is in fossil-based sectors due to the sparsity of biomass energy density and reduced cost of technology.

Some of the advantages of small-scale processes are outlined in terms of reduced transportation costs through the use of local resources, farmer benefits, storage, and logistical ease, and better capabilities in re-using waste and heat (Bruins & Sanders, 2012). These are expected to have lower initial investments and operational costs, lower energy requirements, and less capital-intensive technology (Susmozas, Moreno, Romero-García, Manzanares, & Ballesteros, 2018).

Small-scale biorefineries are typically deployed locally (near feedstock sources) and in rural areas. This contributes to the decentralization of the processing chain and possibly establishes deeper collaboration bonds with farmers and suppliers of biomass. It is this alignment and close cooperation that enables the agility capabilities of the system (company, supply chain).

The single large-scale facility can be split into several smaller ones by leveraging local sources of feedstock and creating an interconnected network of biorefineries. Using distributed manufacturing to promote decentralization by addressing location and scale in terms of technology, processes, systems, and business strategies (Vladimirova et al., n.d.). Collaborative approaches may facilitate production escalation by downstream integration and processing of flows (Günther et al., 2014).

The modularity comes into play as several production units can be added to up-scale the production process as needed, and removed, to de-scale the process. Designing a modularity system may favour agility by implementing several singular low-cost but highly effective modules (Bramsiepe et al., 2012). These modules can be (re)deployed depending on the locally available biomass and contain new conversion processes adapted to the product being produced. This can be linked with the micro-factory concept which integrates automatised production of customised products, delivered on-demand, in which capacity is increased by embedment in a network with other micro-factories (Okazaki, Mishima, and, & Ashida, 2004).

Role of IoT and Information Technologies

Information technologies are fundamental tools for agile systems, as it allows the integration of processes, technology, people, and organizations (Gunasekaran, 1999). Those technologies promote the creation of virtual-based systems, essential for deepening supply-buyer collaborations, and forecasting and satisfying market demands. An agile biorefinery urges to be in constant awareness of the state of the supply given its scale and localized production. Data analytics and the use of I4.0 to sustain and validate operations are likely to have a significant role in streamlining the biorefinery supply chain and operations and optimising purchasing and production activities.

A good example of these synergies is the HereWear H2020 project (“HereWear: Bio-based local sustainable circular wear,” 2022) which works exactly in integrating digitalised production at a local scale for on-demand textile production and clothing goods. It may have a glimpse of what is required to successfully integrate and transition to agile and restorative biorefining.

Key factors for Agile biorefineries: enablers and barriers

Since the literature diverges in the definition of key factors, two concepts that limit the boundaries of the enablers and barriers have been followed. An enabler is a factor that facilitates and supports the concretization of symbiotic synergies. On the other hand, a barrier is a factor that hinders or obstructs the development of symbiotic synergies (Henriques, Ferrão, Castro, & Azevedo, 2021). Enablers and barriers can be presented in various dimensions and levels. For the purpose of this study, five fundamental dimensions have been suggested where the enablers and barriers can take place. These fundamental dimensions are policy & regulation, environmental, social, business, and logistics & management.

Main enablers for AB

Regarding the identification of the enablers, our results present 10 different enablers, distributed in 4 fundamental dimensions (environmental, social, business and logistics & management).

Figure 2 Main enablers for Agile bio refineries

Business

Among the main enablers that can be highlighted in the business category for agile biorefineries, is the multi-applicability that this plant will have. Since, due to the nature of the proposed concept, these plants can process and value various streams/ feedstock and convert them into biofuels, fuels, energy, and other products, thus presenting multiple applications (Ghatak, 2011). One of the main motivations that drive the increase in the promotion of biorefineries in recent years has been the ability to generate income and reduce costs that this type of unit presents. It is expected that the AB also has the potential to reduce operational costs such as feedstock cost reduction and also has the ability to create value through the development of high value products (Lane, 2020). Another fundamental aspect of this dimension is the increase in competitiveness since, similar to biorefineries, the competitiveness of this plant is based on the balance between the production of bio-products and bio-materials of high value/low volume and high volume/low biofuels value (LNEG, 2019).

Environmental

In the environmental dimension, the main enabler presented is the contribution to the reduction of greenhouse gas emissions (GHG), for the reduction of organic waste deposition in landfills. Nevertheless, there are other GHG saving opportunities, for instance, GHG saving associated to the production of heat and electricity and other bioproducts (LNEG, 2019). On the other hand, another important factor is the high biodegradability of potential feedstocks to be valorized. Those biomasses are generally low or non-toxicity, and biocompatibility, not causing risks to the environment and animals, plants, and humans, which increases their potential to be used in various products.

Social

The growing consumer awareness and especially the customer pressure on sustainable development are one of the major enablers in the social. A growing consumer preference for 'green' products is observed, coupled with a growing awareness of the need for action regarding carbon emission reduction (European Commission, 2021) (European Commission, 2019). Another relevant enabler in this regard is the non-harmful solution that this plant presents since Bio-based chemicals are sometimes considered non-harmful, and non-toxic since they originate from nature. Some bio-based solvents are non-toxic and harmless.

Logistics and management

The use of feedstock from several sources, such as agro-food and non-agro-food sectors in cross-sectorial exchanges (Lignocellulosic materials, green fertilizers, and other farm residues kitchen waste, agro-food waste, industrial waste, and forestry wastes) represent a major enabler for AB. The use of

waste, reduction of GHG emission, and reduction of raw materials extraction also represents a considerable advantage.

Main barriers for AB

Regarding the identification of the barriers, our results present 10 different barriers, distributed in 4 fundamental dimensions (Policy & regulations, social, business, and logistics & management).

Figure 3 Main challenges for Agile bio refineries

Business barriers

Concerning business barriers, the lack of cost competitiveness for some EU countries due to higher labor costs affecting CAPEX and OPEX, higher taxes, higher energy costs, and limited low cost biomass feedstocks compared to some other regions in the world, is one of the major barriers in this category (Charles et al., 2013; European Commission, 2021). Another issue emerges is the entrance in existing markets since many of the potential feedstock are already valorized locally or are directed to waste management and landfilling.

Policy and regulations

Among the main regulatory barriers that various countries face in the implementation of biorefineries is the lack of standards and lack of regulation (European Commission, 2021), which ends up hindering

the appropriate promotion of these plants, especially in the initial phase (planning and creation). The result of this study suggests that ABs face similar impediments due to the nature of the concept.

In the same line of thought, one of the problems that we consider will be common in the promotion of these plants, is the existence of regulations, which are an impediment to the recovery of wastes (Ladu, 2018). The waste streams usually have a non-uniform classification, due to the diversity of materials such as waste, residue, or coproduct. This fact leads to loopholes that cannot be addressed by national legislation alone. The ABs will function from the recovery of various feedstock, many of which will be classified as waste. We foresee similar regulation barriers to those faced by other models such as industrial symbiosis and the circular economy in the industry.

Social

Since the concept of AB is still new, our research suggests that in the initial phases of promotion, a major barrier is the lack of knowledge and awareness especially in the benefits that this plant can produce (economic and environmental benefits), especially by SMEs. On the other hand, the lack of technical knowledge and technical expertise required to develop AB will be an important barrier to overcome in this process.

Logistics and management

All bio-based product pathways, to varying degrees, have near-term concerns about feedstock supply and mid-long term concerns over feedstock availability (European Commission, 2021). One of the major concerns that emerge in this dimension is the supply security due to the variability of the availability.

4. Discussion and conclusions

Discussion

Regarding the first research question that refers to the common definition for AB, the paper achieves a contribution to the common definition of AB and identifies the fundamental characteristics of AB. The authors achieved a first draft of a common definition for AB and its main characteristics. The authors consider that Agile biorefineries are flexible plants, where a reconfiguration of the process is achieved by switching equipment inside a single standalone plant, therefore they achieve this agility by adapting configurations, varying feedstocks, and even changing operating conditions throughout time. An agile biorefinery involves a relatively low capital investment modular (adaptable) facility, deployed locally (uses local, short-distance available resources), capable of utilizing different feedstocks (flexible), including wastes, in a small-scale but high yield production, which works in tandem and focusing in generating value across all stakeholders. Seven characteristics of AB were identified, namely: Multiples local stocks (i), Flexible and adaptable production (ii), waste-free (iii), multiple high-value products (iv), supplied buyer integration (v), data-driven support (vi), and modular facility (vii).

Regarding the second research question that refers to the key factors in the implementation process of AB, through our research 10 enablers and 10 barriers were identified that could potentially appear in the implementation process of agile biorefineries. These 20 key factors are distributed in various fundamental dimensions such as Policy & regulations, environmental, social, business, and logistics & management.

Conclusion

An agile biorefinery is a biorefinery that is built to thrive in an uncertain environment, benefitting from small-scale localized production with easy to implement technologies that are feedstock flexible. Working in a small-scale environment requires a closer connection between the sourcing of materials and wastes and the production steps at the biorefinery. A network of localized biorefineries is formed through information systems and integrated with downstream industries for the concomitant production of value-added products and biofuels on a global scale.

This paper achieves the first common definition of this concept that was built by the main characteristics addressed. In the second part of the paper, the key factors (Enablers and barriers) for the implementation process of AB were identified and addressed.

Without disregarding the results obtained in this study, we consider that this study had some limitations due to its nature. The definition of AB, fundamental characteristics, and key factors was based on methods such as observation, literature review, and expert consultation. The authors consider that a real case validation will strengthen the results presented in this study.

Acknowledgment: This work has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 810764, and the EPSRC UK Manufacturing Symbiosis NetworkPlus (UKMSN+) [grant number EP/S036091/1].

References

- Bauer, F., Coenen, L., Hansen, T., McCormick, K., & Palgan, Y. V. (2017). Technological innovation systems for biorefineries: a review of the literature. *Biofuels, Bioproducts and Biorefining*. <https://doi.org/10.1002/bbb.1767>
- Bramsiepe, C., Sievers, S., Seifert, T., Stefanidis, G. D., Vlachos, D. G., Schnitzer, H., ... Schembecker, G. (2012). Low-cost small scale processing technologies for production applications in various environments—Mass produced factories. *Chemical Engineering and Processing: Process Intensification*, 51, 32–52. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cep.2011.08.005>
- Bruins, M. E., & Sanders, J. P. M. (2012). Small-scale processing of biomass for biorefinery. *Biofuels, Bioproducts and Biorefining*, 6(2), 135–145. <https://doi.org/10.1002/bbb.1319>
- Charles, C., Gerasimchuk, I., Bridle, R., Moerenhout, T., Asmelash, E., & Laan, T. (2013). Biofuels: At What Cost? A review of costs and benefits of EU biofuel policies. *International Institute for*

Sustainable Development.

- ElMaraghy, H. A. (2005). Flexible and reconfigurable manufacturing systems paradigms. *International Journal of Flexible Manufacturing Systems*, 17(4), 261–276. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10696-006-9028-7>
- European Commission. (2019). *Bio-based products – from idea to market*. <https://doi.org/10.2777/305874>
- European Commission. (2021). *EU Biorefinery Outlook to 2030*. <https://doi.org/10.2777/103465>
- Ghatak, H. R. (2011). Biorefineries from the perspective of sustainability: Feedstocks, products, and processes. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2011.07.034>
- Gunasekaran, A. (1999). Agile manufacturing: A framework for research and development. *International Journal of Production Economics*, 62(1–2), 87–105. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0925-5273\(98\)00222-9](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0925-5273(98)00222-9)
- Günther, T., Tobias, D. P., Jaqueline, D.-G., Jens, P., Michael, S., John, B., ... BOCHMANN, D. M. D. J. (2014). *Biomethane: Status and Factors Affecting Market Development and Trade*. IEA Bioenergy.
- Henriques, J., Ferrão, P., Castro, R., & Azevedo, J. (2021). Industrial Symbiosis: A Sectoral Analysis on Enablers and Barriers. *Sustainability*. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su13041723>
- HereWear: Bio-based local sustainable circular wear. (2022).
- Houngbé, M., Barthe-Delanoë, A. M., & Négny, S. (2019). A systemic approach for agile biorefineries. In *Computer Aided Chemical Engineering*. <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-12-818634-3.50254-X>
- Igbokwe, V. C., Ezugworie, F. N., Onwosi, C. O., Aliyu, G. O., & Obi, C. J. (2022). Biochemical biorefinery: A low-cost and non-waste concept for promoting sustainable circular bioeconomy. *Journal of Environmental Management*, 305, 114333. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvman.2021.114333>
- Koren, Y., Heisel, U., Jovane, F., Moriwaki, T., Pritschow, G., Ulsoy, G., & Van Brussel, H. (1999). Reconfigurable Manufacturing Systems. *CIRP Annals*, 48(2), 527–540. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0007-8506\(07\)63232-6](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0007-8506(07)63232-6)
- Ladu, L. (2018). *Standards and Regulations for the Bio-based Industry: Identification of technological trends in selected value chains*. Retrieved from <https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/documents/downloadPublic?documentIds=080166e5b917193c&appId=PPGMS>
- Lane, J. (2020). 5 Ways to Reduce Costs in Integrated Biorefineries: The Digest's 2020 Multi-Slide Guide to Enabling Lower-Cost Biofuels.
- LNEG. (2019). *Biorefineries*. Retrieved from <https://www.lneg.pt/en/area/energy/bioenergy/biorefineries/>

- Naik, S. N., Goud, V. V., Rout, P. K., & Dalai, A. K. (2010). Production of first and second generation biofuels: A comprehensive review. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, *14*(2), 578–597. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2009.10.003>
- Nizami, A. S., Rehan, M., Waqas, M., Naqvi, M., Ouda, O. K. ., Shahzad, K., ... Pant, D. (2017). Waste biorefineries: Enabling circular economies in developing countries. *Bioresource Technology*, *241*, 1101–1117. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biortech.2017.05.097>
- Okazaki, Y., Mishima, and, N., & Ashida, K. (2004). Microfactory—Concept, History, and Developments. *Journal of Manufacturing Science and Engineering*, *126*(4), 837–844. <https://doi.org/10.1115/1.1823491>
- Olguin-Maciel, E., Singh, A., Chable-Villacis, R., Tapia-Tussell, R., & Ruiz, H. A. (2020). Consolidated Bioprocessing, an Innovative Strategy towards Sustainability for Biofuels Production from Crop Residues: An Overview. *Agronomy*, *10*(11), 1834. <https://doi.org/10.3390/agronomy10111834>
- Pinales-Márquez, C. D., Rodríguez-Jasso, R. M., Araújo, R. G., Loredó-Treviño, A., Nabarlatz, D., Gullón, B., & Ruiz, H. A. (2021). Circular bioeconomy and integrated biorefinery in the production of xylooligosaccharides from lignocellulosic biomass: A review. *Industrial Crops and Products*, *162*, 113274. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.indcrop.2021.113274>
- Ree, R. van, & Jong, E. de. (2019). Task 42. Biorefining in a future BioEconomy. In *The IEA Bioenergy Task 42*.
- Sims, R. E. H., Mabee, W., Saddler, J. N., & Taylor, M. (2010). An overview of second generation biofuel technologies. *Bioresource Technology*, *101*(6), 1570–1580. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biortech.2009.11.046>
- Sun, Z., Bottari, G., Afanasenko, A., Stuart, M. C. A., Deuss, P. J., Fridrich, B., & Barta, K. (2018). Complete lignocellulose conversion with integrated catalyst recycling yielding valuable aromatics and fuels. *Nature Catalysis*, *1*(1), 82–92. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41929-017-0007-z>
- Susmozas, A., Moreno, A. D., Romero-García, J. M., Manzanares, P., & Ballesteros, M. (2018). Designing an olive tree pruning biorefinery for the production of bioethanol, xylitol and antioxidants: a techno-economic assessment. *Holzforchung*, *73*(1), 15–23. <https://doi.org/10.1515/hf-2018-0099>
- Takkellapati, S., Li, T., & Gonzalez, M. A. (2018). An overview of biorefinery-derived platform chemicals from a cellulose and hemicellulose biorefinery. *Clean Technologies and Environmental Policy*, *20*(7), 1615–1630. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10098-018-1568-5>
- Ubando, A. T., Felix, C. B., & Chen, W.-H. (2020). Biorefineries in circular bioeconomy: A comprehensive review. *Bioresource Technology*, *299*, 122585. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biortech.2019.122585>
- Villemont, C., Lemire, P.-O., Delcroix, B., Boëns, B., Mangin, P., & Barnabé, S. (2017). Policy Brief - Biorefinery Design: Aligning Feedstocks, Supply Chains, and Production Technologies.

BioFuelNet - Policy Brief, (July).

Vladimirova, D., Geissdoerfer, M., Yang, M., Zaki, M., Turner, C., & Tiwari, A. (n.d.). *A conceptual framework for sustainable re-distributed manufacturing business models based on data-driven decision making*. British Academy of Management (BAM) Conference 2017.

Xu, J., Li, C., Dai, L., Xu, C., Zhong, Y., Yu, F., & Si, C. (2020). Biomass Fractionation and Lignin Fractionation towards Lignin Valorization. *ChemSusChem*, 13(17), 4284–4295. <https://doi.org/10.1002/cssc.202001491>